

AESTHETICIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT FOR FUTURE DESIGNERS IN INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Within academic discussions, significant attention revolves around the concept of enhancing the environment aesthetically. Scholars propose defining this process as actively altering and supplementing elements of reality to elevate visual impact, explore new levels of aesthetic depth, and transmission of personal assessment of the beauty of nature, everyday life, works of art, etc. Highlighting its cultural dimensions, researchers underscore the inherent transformations embedded within this process. Aestheticizing the educational environment entails engaging higher education students in aesthetic exploration, the expression of aesthetic sentiments, the application of previously acquired aesthetic knowledge, and active involvement in creative endeavors. Recognizing these transformations underscores the crucial demonstration of an individual's spiritual essence and creative abilities, pivotal for the proper evolution within design education systems.

Keywords: aesthetics, aestheticization, educational environment, aestheticization of educational environment, future designers.

Formulation of the problem. The development of education is closely related to solving the problems of improving the aesthetic quality of the educational environment. It is necessary that students of higher education perceive, understand and appreciate the beauty, harmony, perfection that surrounds them, take an active part in the aesthetic transformation of the surrounding world. The focus of modern education on educating individuals with a high degree of aesthetic sensibility is gaining relevance. In the context of training future designers in institutions of higher education, it is important to use all available methods and means for introducing aesthetic elements into the educational environment.

Analysis of recent publications. The concept of introducing aesthetics into the educational environment was one of the first to be presented in T. Campanelli's work «The City of the Sun» (1623) as an idea of the ideal organization of the human community within the limits of aesthetic order, harmony, and perfection. This trend persists and is still actively developing in European pedagogical theory and practice. In the Ukrainian scientific and educational environment, significant progress in the study of this issue took place relatively recently. The basis for this undertaking was laid by such figures as H. Skovoroda (1961), V. Sukhomlynskyi (1976). There's a growing emphasis on the pivotal role of aesthetics in shaping both personal and socially significant qualities in individuals. Within contemporary Ukrainian pedagogical theory and practice, there's a notable shift towards integrating aesthetics into the educational framework. This shift has garnered significant attention from philosophers, cultural scientists, educators, and psychologists such as I. Zyazyun, O. Berlach, O. Demyanchuk, A. Chyurskyi, and G. Shevchenko.

The goal is to determine the methods of introducing aesthetic elements into the educational process of future designers in higher educational institutions.

The main part. In psychological and pedagogical research, the concept of «aestheticization» is gaining ground, defined as the process of imbuing any objective

entity with an aesthetic form through the influence of aesthetics on an individual. Aestheticization is viewed as a means of structuring the educational process or as a fundamental educational principle. While there's a consensus among scholars regarding the integration of aesthetic elements into educational objectives, tasks, and overall organization, various experts such as O. Demyanchuk, A. Chihurskyi, and O. Berlach propose viewing the aestheticization of an educational institution as both a process and an outcome stemming from the inclusion of aesthetic components in the realm of education and training. Their perspective highlights how this inclusion contributes significantly to cultivating aesthetic consciousness, fostering an aesthetic worldview, and nurturing students' ability to make aesthetic judgments within higher education.

In higher education institutions, an integral aspect of the pedagogical process is the educational setting or atmosphere. This environment covers a number of factors, including material and technical aspects, sanitary and hygienic conditions, ergonomic requirements, aesthetic elements, psychological and pedagogical aspects. All these factors together contribute to the organization of the educational process in the process of professional training. It is necessary that these conditions meet the spiritual and social needs of the participants of the educational process, in particular cognitive, aesthetic, cultural and social requirements, as well as the needs for interpersonal communication.

Attempts to define the concept of «environment» in the context of educational institutions of different levels have given rise to several terms in pedagogical theory. These terms cover general concepts such as «cultural environment», «socio-cultural environment», «educational environment» or «educational space». They also extend to more specific terms such as «pedagogical environment», «pedagogical actions», «educational environment», «aesthetic environment», «cultural-humanitarian environment», «aesthetic-pedagogical environment», «aesthetic-pedagogical space»,

«artistic and aesthetic environment», «aesthetic environment of pedagogical activity», etc. Sometimes in such cases, the terms «pedagogical-aesthetic atmosphere», «aesthetic field», etc. can be used. These specific designations highlight aspects of the content and emphasize the various qualities of the educational environment, which indicates its multifaceted nature. They also emphasize the significant value of aesthetic elements in a complex educational environment, which is important for the successful implementation of the pedagogical process in the modern educational environment.

The aestheticization of the educational environment for future designers is of crucial importance for the promotion of innovation and enables the acquisition of professional competences with a priority focus on the laws of aesthetics. Let's identify some key elements that should be considered when creating an educational environment for future designers.

Diverse workspaces: Designers benefit from a variety of workspaces. Open collaborative areas facilitate the exchange of ideas, while individual workspaces allow for deep concentration. Such a dynamic environment that can be easily adapted to the different needs of design projects is essential.

Inspiring surroundings: Include elements that inspire creativity, such as artwork, nature and innovative design. Consider using natural light, plants and aesthetically pleasing decor to create an atmosphere that encourages creativity.

Technology Integration: Designers must have access to the latest tools and software. High-quality hardware and software are essential for project work and availability of these tools should be a priority.

Collaborative space: Design is often a collaborative process. Provide spaces for brainstorming, projecting and discussing ideas. Interactive whiteboards, projectors and digital collaboration tools should serve as tools in this process.

Materials and Resources: Designers must have access to a wide range of materials, from traditional art objects to modern fabrication tools such as 3D printers, innovative printing equipment, and more. This allows for experimentation and prototyping.

Comfort and ergonomics: comfortable furniture and ergonomic workplaces are vital. Designers spend long hours on the job, and discomfort can hinder creativity and productivity.

Learning Opportunities: Continuous learning and professional development should be obtained from seminars, courses and resources on industry trends that will allow designers to implement self-education activities.

Academic freedom: designers must be given some freedom to manage their time and projects. Autonomy can produce innovative decision-making and self-improvement processes.

A space for feedback and criticism: it is necessary to create a culture of feedback and criticism. Designers can benefit from peer reviews and constructive criticism. Designated seating for these events can be helpful.

Community and Networking: A sense of community among designers needs to be fostered, encouraging communication both within classroom activities and with external design communities. This can lead to new perspectives and cooperation.

Library collection: a well-chosen literature and resource collection of design-related books, magazines, and resources can be a valuable resource for the creation, implementation, and interpretation of creative projects.

Moodboards and demo areas: Create spaces where designers can showcase their projects, create moodboards, and display inspiring visuals. It can promote creativity and serve as a source of motivation.

Conclusions and prospects for further research. The educational environment of a higher education institution should act as a catalyst for the personal growth and development of future designers. Undoubtedly, aesthetic elements, such as beauty, harmony of the environment where professional training takes place, play a special role in the implementation of this process. It is also necessary to take into account a number of factors, including material and technical aspects, sanitary and hygienic conditions, ergonomic requirements, aesthetic elements, psychological and pedagogical aspects, which will encourage future designers to actively creative study and aesthetic evaluation of works of art and design.

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